

THE CREATION OF LIFE’S ILLUSION IN VISUAL INTERPRETATIONS OF DRAMA AND MUSICAL DRAMA (EXEMPLIFIED BY PERFORMANCES OF THE 1930S)

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***Abstract.** The article examines the development of scenographic art in Uzbekistan through the example of theatrical productions of the 1930s. It explores the techniques and expressive means characteristic of this period, analyzes the productions of leading theaters, and studies the activities of stage designers.*

***Keywords:** Scenography, artist, set design, technique, theater, directing, dramaturgy, music, costume, stage.*

The 1930s were a complex period for theatrical art, particularly for the art of stage decoration. Theater art took steps towards professionalism. However, culture, especially theatrical art, began to take on a political tone. All creative explorations were suppressed because they did not respond to the calls of socialism. This pushed back the process of professionalization in Uzbek theatrical art.

These contradictions were also reflected in the art of stage decoration. The play “History Speaks” by Ziyoy Said and Nazir Safarov, which addressed the politics of the era and premiered on May 5, 1931, was staged by director M. Uygur and artist G. Lazovskiy. This work became a landmark production of its time and was performed continuously for 20 days after its premiere. Regarding the stage design of the play, theater critic M. Rahmonov states: “The walls of the dimly lit rooms where secret meetings were held were covered with black fabric. The powerful spotlight would intermittently illuminate the black masks of the conspirators, a human skull, or a hand with twisted fingers. During the performance, trenches would silently open, and those who disobeyed were thrown into the depths of the earth...” (1, c. 100). The scenic designer’s dim lighting of the performance space stems from the essence of the work. Indeed, throughout the play, there were numerous scenes depicting clandestine encounters between traitors and the forces opposing them. The use of movable side decorations and the precise division of space along the width and height of the stage, in relation to the backdrop, demonstrates the artist’s skill.

In the 1930s, regional theaters experienced a surge in the development of stage art due to the influx of actors and directors who had graduated from the first and second Moscow studios, studied at the studio established in the Hamza Theater, or trained at the Moscow Institute of Theatre Arts, like Q. Khojaev, along with skilled artists. For instance, at the Andijan theater, director M. Muhamedov, composer T. Jalilov, playwright K. Yashin, artists P. Koval and N. Okhunov, and a group of talented actors gained experience in using set design during the staging process. They worked on musical dramas such as “Layli and Majnun” and “Halima”, the musical comedy “Arshin mol olon”, and productions addressing socio-political themes including “Comrades”, “Victory”, “Defeat”, “Inside”, “We Burn” and “History Speaks”. While the influence of the capital's theatrical decor was often noticeable in their earlier staged productions,

the theater strived to follow its own unique path in the plays staged during the second half of the 1930s, including “Cunning and Love”, “The Inspector General”, “Intrigue and Love”, “The Rich Man and the Servant”, “Maysara’s Case”, “Kholiskhon” and “Gulsara”.

In the play “O’rtoqlar” (“Friends”) (a work by K. Yashin, 1930), for example, director M. Muhamedov divides the characters into two groups. This is evident in their external appearance, costumes, makeup, and acting performances. The set decorations are also not far removed from the reality of life. They are presented in a slightly exaggerated form. For instance, the cotton boll was so enormous that a group of people could sit in its shadow. Similarly, apples and grapes were crafted to be five to six times larger than their natural size. The director believed that such a method would attract viewers. In the play “Victory” (a work by S. Husayn, 1931), M. Mukhamedov’s directorial approach also encouraged the artist to use an exaggerated style in the stage design. M. Tojizoda describes the stage design of the “Victory” performance as follows: “A small platform in the middle of the stage. Stairs rise 3-4 meters up on both sides of it. They lead to a domed circular platform. Between the lower and upper platforms is a canvas. It depicts a view of mountainous hills. The scene is covered with a delicate veil, and the hills are illuminated by moonlight. Qunduz and other characters move about in this scene. The audience hears the voices of the actors during the scene of Qunduz’s execution. However, they see not the actors themselves, but rather the outlines of their figures. (2, c. 71-72).

It is worth emphasizing that the Hamza Theater has served as a laboratory for the provincial theaters in their explorations of dramaturgy, directing, acting, and stage design.

The decorations and costumes of the Hamza Theater in the 1930s and 1940s are largely associated with the artist Hamidulla Ikromov (1909 - 1964). He studied at the pedagogical technical school and the art studio of the Tashkent Art Museum, and later enhanced his skills in Leningrad. From 1931, as the chief artist of the theater, he collaborated with directors such as Mannon Uygur, Yatim Bobojonov, and Alexander Ginzburg, designing sets for dozens of plays. The actors’ costumes were created based on his sketches. While designing the sets for plays created in the 1930s, such as “Rustam” (U. Ismailov), “The Mask Was Torn” (Z. Fatkhulin), “Springtime Love” (K. Trenev), and “The Rich Man and the Servant” (Hamza), H. Ikromov grew as an artist, and his understanding of scenery and costumes deepened. In the creative work of the artist H. Ikromov, a tendency towards narrative and detail in portraying life on stage is noticeable. This style, which accurately reflects life and was used in both performances on national themes and stage interpretations of translated works, led to the creation of illusory scenery. This approach allowed the actors to depict the reality of life described in the drama and portray the characters' images in both detailed and generalized ways. In particular, Ziyoy Said’s work “Niqob yirtildi” (“The Mask Was Torn”), which premiered on June 6, 1932, was highly regarded as the first independent work of the artist H. Ikromov. The authentic artistic design of the stage encouraged the actors to perform their roles accurately within the existing conditions.

In the play “The Rich Man and the Servant” (a work by Hamza, revised by K. Yashin, May 13, 1939), the scenery, costumes, props, and the overall environmental depiction, as well as the external appearances of the participants, are designed to resolve the social conflict, showcasing the best characteristics of H. Ikromov’s work. “The authenticity of the setting, the precision and familiarity of everyday elements brought the characters closer to the audience, astonishing viewers with its truthful portrayal of the recent past” (3, c. 19). The artist employed the narrative style of the pavilion decoration system in the performance.

The curtain opens, revealing Solihboy’s inner courtyard to the audience. On the right side are two grand houses, and on the left is one. The houses have verandas in front. At the back is a

gate leading outside, to the left is the kitchen, and there's a pathway leading to the garden. The audience's eyes are dazzled by the intricately carved and patterned doors, and precious items arranged on columns and in alcoves. The veranda stage is covered with Turkmen carpets and velvet quilts. Such a scene, realistically depicting the true appearance of a wealthy household, primarily helps to emphasize the contrast between external pomp and luxury and the moral corruption of the people living in that courtyard. Furthermore, the staging director Yatim Bobojonov, with the assistance of artist H. Ikromov, has succeeded in immersing both the actors and the audience in the atmosphere of the recent past.

Solihboy's guesthouse (Act 2), the house allocated to Jamila (Act 4), and Qodirqul mingboshi's courtyard (Act 3) are also portrayed as lavish. The staging director and artist paid serious attention not only to the scenery but also to the accurate representation of costumes, props, and ethnographic customs such as offering hookahs, laying the tablecloth, greeting, and bowing, not only in the play “The Rich Man and the Servant” but also in other performances. This approach was regarded as a passion for depicting everyday life. At times, it was even attributed to naturalism, which is not accurate. The director and artist believed that the artistic decorations, furnishings, and costumes themselves should evoke delight in the audience and celebrate the mastery of folk craftsmen and seamstresses. However, this is not the only purpose of these auxiliary elements. The main goal is to accurately reflect the socio-historical environment and help to deeply reveal the content of the work” (4, c. 9-10).

Artist H. Ikromov emphasizes everyday details on stage based on the director's vision. However, accurately portraying such minor details has helped to sufficiently reveal the theme. At this point, harmony between the director's solution and the artist's idea emerged in the play. Artist H. Ikromov was able to fully express Y. Bobojonov's direction in the performance, creating a stage image in the theatrical space. This performance demonstrates the increased emphasis on everyday detail in the decorative arts of this period.

By the 1930s, artists specializing in set design emerged in musical theatre (musical drama, opera, and ballet). At the State Musical Drama Theater (1929-1939) led by Muhiddin Qori Yoqubov and the Alisher Navoi Grand Academic Opera and Ballet Theater (1939-1945), artists such as Sh. Shorahimov, Ye. Baranovsky, M. Gvozdikov, V. Afanasyev, and A. Dulevsky worked to ensure that the stage decorations and actors' costumes were proportionate to the on-stage actions and characters, maintaining a professional standard. The set design and costumes for “Buron” (music by M. Ashrafiy and S. Vasilenko, libretto by Yashin, 1939), the first Uzbek opera, were created based on M. Gvozdikov's sketches. However, in musical drama, opera, and ballet theaters, the artist Sh. Shorahimov designed the sets for most of the national stage productions. Performances such as “Farhod and Shirin” (1933), “The Storm” (1934), “Gulsara” (1936), and “Layli and Majnun” (1933) serve as evidence of this.

Especially, the decorations of the play “Farhod and Shirin” were created with love. The treasury, mountain views, Khusrau's tent (scene 3) attracted attention with the proportionality of colors, the poetic expression of space. Although Sh. Shorahimov's plans in drawings and models were not always realized, his creative pursuits had a fruitful impact on the work of artists working in regional theaters. For instance, the artist I. Margunov, inspired by the work of Sh. Shorahimov, designed the set for the play “Farhod and Shirin”, staged at the Kashkadarya Regional Theater, in an elaborate manner, paying special attention to external effects (5, c. 109). The artist primarily employed the visual decoration style typically used in musical theaters.

Sh. Shorahimov set himself the goal of revealing the tragic plight of Eastern women in the play “Gulsara”. In the final of the work, as a symbol of Gulsara's victory and her liberation,

the women throw their paranjas into what appears to be a blazing fire. This final scene was also preserved in the revised version of 1937.

In general, during the second half of the 1930s and the years of World War II, artists such as Sh. Shorahimov, H. Ikromov, S. Milenin, I. Valdenberg, and D. Ushakov made significant contributions to the activities of Uzbek theater, particularly in the high-quality production of sets and costumes. At the Hamza Theater, T.P. Suleymonova set an example with her creative approach to tailoring costumes based on the artist's sketches, ensuring they suited both the performer and the character. In makeup artistry, B.P. Luchikhin gained recognition for his work.

During this period, interest in another trend in stage practice, “naturalism” intensified. Direct replicas of streets and houses began to be incorporated into stage decorations. Theatrical ethnography and everyday scenes became clearly visible. According to D. Rakhimov, an Honored Artist of Uzbekistan, “real horses were brought onto the stage... In the play ‘Arshin mol olon’ the horse brought on for the scene of the girl’s abduction nearly killed Shahodat Rakhimova, who was playing the role of Gulchehra” (6, c. 89).

In the 1930s, theater artists employed volumetric and pavilion-style set designs, along with narrative, pictorial, constructivist, lighting, and improvisational game-like techniques, as well as simultaneous and conditional decorative methods in their performances. However, these were difficult years when the theater began to struggle against the trends of formalism, naturalism, and constructivism. At that time, the practice of reflecting life only through realistic means was recognized and considered to align with the style of socialist realism. For this reason, during this period, stage productions often utilized decorations that accurately reflected life and conveyed a realistic stage environment, historically accurate and realistic costumes, as well as ethnographically precise equipment and objects. This realism and accuracy became the main criteria for evaluating the work of artists. The primary goal was to create an illusion of the place and time of events on the stage.

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